

Network Self-Management Pseudo-Predictability based on Case-Based Reasoning

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Abstract

Network self-management, among other objectives, looks for solutions (systems, frameworks and/or strategies) in which the human intervention is drastically reduced in the analysis and planning of new network states, which in turn, is based on a set of SLAs (Service Level Agreement) definitions and traffic profile. The self-management system/framework has to find a solution meeting SLA and traffic requirements within a reasonable computational time (execution time) in order to achieve a near real time operation. In general, it is necessary to adopt approaches based on reasoning and learning in self-management systems in order to avoid and/or reduce human intervention [1]. As such, self-management systems/frameworks do require the storage of network states. In this context, it is important to identify critical states and, if possible, to predict when they will occur in order to facilitate the self-management process. In this paper, a proposal for pseudo-predictability based on Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) is presented. The pseudo-predictability CBR method considers previous network states to infer future network state scenario. It was developed for the self-management framework defined in [2] and, in general, further promotes the scalability of self-managed systems.

Keywords: Predictability, Self-Management, Case-Based Reasoning, CBR.

1 Introduction

The computation of a new network state (new optimized configuration or new state after failure) having as a basic requirement the optimization of resources like, for instance, link utilization, may require an huge amount of processing time eventually unacceptable for self-management systems [3]. As an example, the computation of a new network state upon link and/or node failure for a domain with hundreds of nodes may typically require minutes to converge to a solution in a less performing machine. As such, management systems dealing with huge network topologies have a tendency to adopt offline solutions with some help expected from the manager himself.

The autonomic management approach for computing new network states (configuration) presented in this paper suggests the use of pseudo-predictability for scenarios involving huge network topologies. The pseudo-predictability approach is effectively coupled with the self-management scalable approach developed in [3]. This self-management system aims to reduce the processing time and try to achieve an on-the-fly computation.

A self-management problem can be generically modeled as a self-management processing system having as entry the actual network state (network parameters) and a set of user, application and/or business requirements. The self-management system developed in [3] generates

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a suitable new network state (configuration) as its output. Its control (high-level management) consists in adjusting the entry requirements set (application, user or business) based on the actual network state. This self-management system will compute and identify the suitable solution (new network state) among the set of all possible existing solutions.

In searching new network solutions (states), an autonomic system may incorporate learning and reasoning techniques [4]. According to [5], during the analysis and planning phases, implemented by the autonomic system decision plane, diverse techniques may be applied such as event correlation, inference, game theory, economic models, decision theory and risk analysis, among the most important ones.

In this context, some computed states may satisfy or not user (entry) requirements. In effect, a new computed state may lead to a critical network state which, for instance, do not fulfill SLAs requirements. As such, it might be useful to predict new network states which can lead to the unsatisfactory overall results and, as such, try to optimize even further the computation of new states in a self-management system.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 02 summarizes the requirements specification for network self-management. Section 03 presents a proposal on how to add learning and reasoning in self-management frameworks with Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) and presents the pseudo-predictability approach. Concluding remarks are presented in section 04.

2 The Requirements Specification for Network Self- Management

Requirement specification in self-management defines aspects that have to be preserved for any new network state computed in response to failure or when targeting network resource optimization. In summary, the main network self-management system requirements are:

- To reduce the allocation time for computing new network states aiming to provide *scalability*;
- To maximize *performability* [6];
- To maximize managed network *survivability* in case of failure (crash); and
- To enforce the *modularity (adaptability)* of the self-management system in relation to different routing and decision algorithms alternatives currently used by networks.

To achieve some or all of these overall objectives various implementation approaches for self-management systems may be adopted. In the framework described in [3], the approach was focused on enhancing scalability and included:

- The implementation of a partitioning technique as a function of the network topology and traffic profile aiming at providing a scalable solution; and
- The incorporation of reasoning and learning techniques in order to enable autonomic decisions.

3 Adding Reasoning, Learning and Predictability in Self-Management Frameworks

As indicated in section II, the autonomic self-management framework developed adopts an event correlation technique in its control plane which belongs to the framework decision plane (Figure 1) [7] [8]. The event correlation technique adopted is a CBR-based solution that uses past experiences to find out new network state solutions [9] [10].

Figure 1: Network Self-Management Model [7] [8]

The CBR technique is similar to the human way of solving problems and, as such, new solutions (network states) are found based on past experience and their similarities (case-based). CBR techniques have the ability to find a new solution in terms of any previous network state and makes use of the 4R algorithm (retrieve, reuse, review and retain) [11] (Figure 2).

Figure 2: 4R Cycle [11]

In CBR a case that occurred in the past corresponds to a stored tuple in problem-solution format [12]. In the network self-management context, a case (CI) is composed by the problems encountered in the managed network (symptoms) (pI) and the respective solution to such problem (sI). The case is generically described as follows:

$$CI = (pI, sI) \tag{1}$$

This basic case description has been extended to promote greater efficiency and flexibility in finding new solutions. In effect, context information was added in order to provide a more flexible case description. As such, problems may occur in different contexts like, for example, a link failure and may cause different reactions depending on the current state of the network (different set of routes/ paths).

The efficiency is promoted in the tuple case representation by eliminating the non-relevant domain-based cases in the current context (topological change or low occurrence of cases). The extended case description tuple is as follows:

$$CI = \{eI, pI, sI, qsI, csI, bsI, tsI\} \quad (2)$$

- eI represents the state of the network;
- pI corresponds to the problem encountered in the state eI ;
- sI indicates the input solution to the problem pI ;
- qsI indicates the quality of the proposed solution, with the quality being indicated by the level of SLA conformance;
- csI indicates the number of occurrences of a CI and is used to verify the occurrence of low utilization cases and may indicate the need to refine the search for new solutions;
- bsI indicates if previously used; and
- tsI indicates the last time occurrence for a case.

The integration of the CBR approach in the self- management framework is realized in terms of two operational cycles: recovery cycle (retrieving solutions) and search cycle (searching new network state solutions). In the recovery cycle, a new network state solution is found based on the similarity between the current network state and a previously stored network states. In the recovery cycle, the control plane executes the functions: Retrieve Cases, selected State Solution and Validator (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Control Plane Cycle

In case no similarity is found, the control plane should look for a new solution using the search cycle. The cycle of searching for new network state solution includes, as defined in [7], a set of computational steps including State Simulator, Performance Analysis and Create Solution. At this point is important to mention that the search cycle is computationally intensive (Figure 3). As the search cycle is computationally intensive, it may become a bottleneck for the autonomic management framework.

In effect, there is a stringent requirement in terms of framework response time (time to find a new network state) that is defined by the administrator. The solution has to be found in a time-frame adequate for the applications supported by the network (requirement) regardless of the managed network complexity (number of nodes).

Promoting predictability in terms of future network states could then be a major benefit for most self-management frameworks that, independently of their implementation, have to execute intensive computation to identify these new states. With the use of CBR, some predictable mapping (Figure 4) may be useful as: displaying a current state probability of leading to a critical state, reducing the number of cases-base through cases occurrence percentage.

As a model and concept for this predictability approach a mapping representation of network states is proposed in a graph G as follows:

- The vertices of the graph G represent the possible network configurations.
- The edges of the graph G represent transitions between network states. The edges are directional and exists an integer value associated that represents how many times state x migrated to state y .
- The graph G has an initial state that indicates the default system configuration.

Figure 4: Network State Graph

Figure 4 illustrates, as an example, an effective application of this predictability model. The management reading of the graph is as follows:

- The state C have 23.07%¹ to go to a critical state (B) that we may avoid;
- This can done by moving to states A and/or D (if they guarantee SLAs) view that 87.10%² of states changes lead to only three states (A, C, D) (60.00% of the cases); and
- Self-management new network state computing scalability could be further improved by reducing the set of possibilities for the on-the-fly computation of new network states.

4 Final Considerations

This paper presented how Case-Based Reasoning approach can be integrated in Network Self-Management Frameworks in order to promote pseudo-predictability provisioning. Pseudo-predictability allows an analysis of future network states and may effective lead to a reduction

¹ $(ECB)/(ECA + ECB + ECD)$

² $(EAC + EAD + ECD + ECA + EDA + EDC)/(sum(E(G)))$

of computational time required by self-management systems. Briefly, this is achieved by the fact that the pseudo-predictability may reduce, at least, part of the brute force approach currently used in which all possible new network states are computed and analyzed.

As such, these types of graphs can be used to predict critical new states and, consequently, may reduce the computational required to compute new solutions in a self-management system. In implementation terms, these graph analysis would effectively remove cases from the database used by the CBR learning and reasoning module at any self-management system.

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